

Racism, Isolation and Parody in UK Contemporary Fiction: The case of Sarah Moss' Summerwater

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1. Abstract

In the year 2020 when Britain underwent one of the most important events in its recent history, being its exit from the European Union, this event receives the name of Brexit. It is through fiction that we are able to express the political and social reality of a country and this is what author Sarah Moss does with her novel, *Summerwater* (2020). It is through Sara Moss' fictional contemporary novel, that we are going to look at two important issues in the current UK social landscape, racism and isolation.

When talking about isolation it is necessary to point out that we are talking about a sentiment of being apart of the European Union as, we will see how British citizens never fully embrace their European identity and that, their exit from the European Union has left them isolated from the rest of Europe as many Europeans look for other places to reside, work or travel due to the restrictions they are imposed by Britain and, we will see how does Moss' witting translate this problem to *Summerwater* as the scene of the book setted in a Scottish cabin park and also and dark nature passages help her to talk about his issue. Racism is also reflected on the book as it has been a problem that has affected the UK for many years and, in the book, we will explore not only the interactions between the ukrainian family with the british characters, but also the interactions between Scottish and English characters as there is tension between them because of Brexit results and common shared history developing a form on "internal racism".

This subject is worth exploring because Racism, Parody and Class are social issues that have seen growth since Brexit was made official. Although Sara Moss' novel *Summerwater* explores other social issues like family or social class, I found the other topics of racism and isolation worth exploring as they are not so talked about.

The objective is to see how *Summerwater* portrays racism and isolation and how this book is a parody of British society as we will prove this by focusing on these two topics that are present in the novel.

Before beginning our analysis of the book we will contextualize the situation of racism and isolation in the UK as it is crucial for the understanding of the novel and the two concepts we are trying to analyze.

2.Racism in the UK

To conduct our analysis on *Summerwater*, we first need to understand how Brexit reinforced racist tendencies. It is in the year 2016, that Britain voted in a referendum if they needed to leave the European Union where it was decided that it was time to say farewell to the EU and, this came as a surprise to many but, I would like to defy that as, Carl and Dennison argue in their text "*The ultimate causes of Brexit: history, culture, and geography*" (2016) "the UK is the least well-integrated EU member state – essentially, the least European country – and that this fact likely stems from certain historical features, which arguably constitute the ultimate causes of Brexit" (1).

It was also during the years that the Brexit as a process started that "The rise of populist nationalism in many parts of the developed world testify to the resurgence of fears around intensified immigration and the renewed power of racism" (Flemen,Savage 233), this new resurgence of racism is not something new as, the racism that intensified during this period of time had been previously built upon the previous racist tendencies that existed in the UK (Rzepnikowska 62).

People who actually voted for Brexit would reveal that their decision was not a matter of economic character but rather an opposition to immigration (Bhambra 222).

2.1 External Racism

This reinforced racist tendencies form what we will name "external racism" as, in *Summerwater* (2020), one of the families come from Ukraine and will face racist comments for their culture and behavior.

These interactions between British characters and the Ukrainian characters will be labeled as "external racism" because of the interaction between an outside culture with the local one. The choosing of a Ukrainian family to be the representation of racism is Sarah Moss' *Summerwater* does not come as a surprise as "East European migrants and majority has not exempted the former from racialisation."(Rzepnikowska 62). This new form of "external racism" also receives the name of "xenophobia" which comes from Greek and means "fear of the guest/stranger"(Rzepnikowska 63).

But why does the Ukrainian family in Summerwater face racism if they are white? Why also British citizens reject Eastern Europeans if they belong to the same ethnicity as them?, The answer to this question relies on the new contemporary meaning of race and how this new racist tendencies built their target as, in his book, *“There Ain’t No Black In The Union Jack”* (1987), Paul Gilroy argues ‘the capacity to link discourses of patriotism, nationalism, xenophobia, Englishness, Britishness, militarism and gender difference into a complex situation which gives “race” its contemporary meaning”(43).

Therefore, we can argue that, in relation to Summerwater (2020), the Sevchenko's social situation with the rest of the lodge's population is based on different concepts as, although they are white, they do not share the same traditions as the rest of the characters and, therefore they will receive racism.

2.2 Internal Racism

“The United Kingdom was described as centralised but not uniform” (McHarg and Mitchell 514) as, one aspect to highlight from Summerwater (2020) is the relation that the English characters have with the Scottish characters as it is noticeable that the Scottish characters show a feeling of disgust and contempt towards the English characters as both Scotland and England.

Sarah Moss released this book in August, 2020 so it is possible for us to establish a connection between many of the events that might have caused tension between the English and the Scottish characters. These two events, apart from the shared history between this lands, could be the Scottish independence referendum that was voted in 2014 as some Scots felt that they had the “sovereign right of the Scottish people to determine the form of Government best suited to their needs”(Kellas 51) and also Brexit as, in 2016 “(...)the Scottish electorate voted by a significantly larger majority—62% to 38%—for the UK, including Scotland, to remain within the European Union” (McEwen 65).

As we previously discussed, UK has been the least integrated country in the European Union and this is one of the reasons that has Brexit to happen but, in Scotland there is a different sentiment in regards to this matter as “Scots appeared more favourable towards European integration than voters in

England, and held a stronger European identity.”(McEwen 68). This European identity of Scotland took more shape during the government of British prime minister Margaret Thatcher as, according to James Mitchell in his book “*The Scottish Question*”(2014), it was the increasing Euroscepticism shown by Thatcher's government that encouraged the Scotland to develop a more tight relationship with the European Union as Scotland established a relationship of “my enemy’s enemy” with the EU which, in the end, ended up in developing a good relationship between Scotland and the EU (231-234).

It is with Scotland and England's historical differences that we can comprehend why the Scottish characters in *Summerwater* (2020) show a hostile attitude towards the English characters.

In conclusion, we have seen that, in the UK, racism attitudes towards outsiders have seen an increase in frequency due to immigration becoming one of the main points and issues of Brexit ideals also, it is Scotland's will of remaining in the EU and also its independence tendencies that have drawn a line between Scots and English citizens. For our next chapter we will explore and analyze the book of *Summerwater* to see how Sarah Moss reflects the UK racism situation through her writing.

3. Summerwater on External Racism

Racism is one of the most present topics in *Summerwater* (2020) as, in the book we can see it becomes the central aspect of some chapters like “*a stone falling*”, “*noise in his body*” or “*a woman sitting on the edge*”.

It also interesting to see that, although in some chapters they are not the main protagonists they are still critiqued and lightly targeted and mentioned like in “*other silent swimmers*” where Claire, who is the main character in this chapter, is in her lodge with her husband Jon and her two kids Pat and Izzie. Although the focus of the topic is to reflect on Claire’s experiences and stressful life as a mother and the free hour she gets from her husband, she will also complain about the way of living and night habits of the Ukrainians where she says “(...) all of them kept awake half the night by the Romanians next door and their loud music.” (101).

Therefore we can conclude that, although they are not very present in some chapters they are sometimes targeted for their way of living and especially

their night partying which will become a central topic of discussion for them in the book.

3.1 Polish, Ukrainians, Romanians or Bulgarians?

Europe is a very big continent and one of the things that characterizes this continent is the amount of great diversity that it possesses.

In his text, "*Nationalism and Identity in Britain and Europe*"(1996), Robin Dennell recalls what author Fernandez-Arnesto says on this book "The Times guide to the peoples of Europe"(1994) as he says that the twenty-five countries of Europe (at the time of the writing of his book) contain hundreds of people that although they have their own language, identity, traditions they might not seek statehood as they are examples of countries that share this explained situation like the UK, which is composed of by English, Scots or Welsh (qtd. in Dennell 23).

Arguing that Europe is a very diverse region also means that although people might live in the same region they will probably share different traditions. In *Summerwater* (2020) it is very noticeable that the Shevchenko family are differently labeled as different eastern Europe nationalities and also that their own identity and traditions are questioned throughout the book as characters like Violetta or her mother would face violent situations when interacting with the rest of the lodge.

It is along many chapters that, although the Shevchenko's come from Ukraine, they will be associated with different eastern European countries like Poland, Bulgaria and Romania. The association that the Shevchenko's receive to Poland happens in the chapter titled "*what it's like being*", where we are introduced to the character of Becky, a Scottish girl who is on holidays with her family at the lodge.

In this chapter, she decides to visit the house of the Shevchenko's where, she hears the mother of the family talking to Violetta in their own language and, she tries to communicate with them as she describes "It sounded a bit like Polish so Becky said "*dzien dobry*" just to see if it worked" (148), this interaction happened because Becky thought that every Eastern European language are almost similar, this shows her lack of knowledge as she ignores the diversity of European languages and its cultures and also, its belief that

they were Polish highlights an unintentional racist situation on her behalf but, although it is innocently racist it bases for believing their Polish are not far fetched as Polish people are the biggest migrant community in the UK with 916,000 registered residents in 2015 (Rzepnikowska 62). This interaction led to a tense encounter between the mother of Violetta and Becky as, firstly we get to know the true nationality of the Sevchenko's as Becky says "Turned out, she is Ukrainian, not Polish" (148) but also, Violetta's mother will defend herself by saying that she pays her taxes and has been living in the UK for twenty years. This highlights her defense mechanisms as she would have probably experienced similar situations.

The second nationality that the Sevchenko's are associated with is "Bulgaria" as Steve, in the chapter "*a woman sitting on the edge*" he makes certain comments and labels them as Bulgarians as, for example he says: "bloody Bulgarians" (181), "Show the Bulgarians they're pissing off everyone" (183) and "(...) if he went round there and told those Bulgarians what's that" (178). These examples show Steve's racist tendencies as he also calls them Romanians and also alludes that they are Polish by asking if they have rap in Poland (180). This sequence of events portray Steve, who is Lola's father, as a racist and ignorant individual and we can get an idea of where Lola gets his hatred from outsiders.

To conclude this chapter, we need to make mention of the most common nation that the Shevchenko's are associated with, Romania as, throughout the book, many characters like Steve or Mary will call them "The Romanians" as, for example, Mary complains about the noise they make, comparing them to the French or Germans (31) or Steve when he complains about the noise (184-185). This tendency to call them "Romanian" portray the xenophobia that the UK citizens have adopted during Brexit as the fear of immigration we talked about before blinds them from meeting their outsider neighbors and decides to call them the nationality they want, portraying the lodge residents as very closed minded individuals, except for Becky who is the only one that learns that they come from Ukraine.

3.2 Shit-chenko

In the chapter titled, "*a stone falling*" we get to meet one of the many kids that appear in the book, Lola, who is a Scottish girl from Glasgow that is enjoying their holidays at the lodge. One day both Lola and his brother Jack go out to play when they meet a dark haired girl called Violetta.

Violetta starts to play with both Jack and Lola and there is a precise moment where she needs help and Lola accepts (73), it is after this event that one of the most aggressively racist encounters will take place on the book as Lola starts to interrogate Violetta as she starts to suspect that she is not from around here, Lola decides to ask her and, it is this very conversation that shows Lola's racist tendencies as, at the end of the chapter Violetta answers Lola's questions and the following interaction happens, "Violetta, says Lola. Violetta who? The girl says some syllables. Shit-chenko, says Lola, Violetta Shit-chenko? Shevchenko, says the girl, Shevchenko"(74).

This first encounter allows us to interpret the inherited racism that Lola has as she tries to make fun of Violetta's surname by changing the first four letters of her surname from "Shevchenko" to "Shit-chenko", after this exchange of words Lola and Jack will adopt a aggressive and violent attitude towards Violetta as, when Violetta asked Lola if she is from Glasgow she responded by saying "its none of your business where I'm from"(74) to which also Jack also acted aggressively as he pointed his "gun" at Violetta, taking aim at her (74). One of the reasons for this attitude from the kids is that they have started to see her as a threat .

This can happen when, as Chan et al. argues in their text "*Understanding the Social and Cultural Bases of Brexit*" (2020) "As regards immigration, it might lead to feelings of cultural loss, even a symbolic threat to the British way of life"(834) also, another reason for this attitude lies in the topic of class as, Lola and Jack come from a family that is probably a working class scottish family previously to brexit this families became very concerned about immigration as the great fluxes of immigration that rose from 1997 to 2004 saw an increase in Eastern European population, and "This influx produced a strong reaction among voters, who became very concerned about rising immigration"(Goodwin 60) so we can comprehend that Lola and Jack might have been influenced by their parents beliefs and concerns on immigration

as we can see Steve's racist tendencies on the chapter titled " *a woman sitting on the edge*"

Lola would continue his aggressive and violent attitude towards Violetta as she would start to blame her for the noise and critique her because her family is disturbing the other cabin residents. When asked where she comes from, Violetta and Lola would have a violent conversation that would leave the little girl on the verge of crying as Violetta said:

"Glasgow, says Violetta. Govanhill. you can see she's going to cry, any minute now. (...) I'm getting sick of this, says Lola, I asked you where you're really from. You're supposed to have left, you know, people like you, did you not get the message?" (75)

By the book's description and Violetta's origin, we can see that she is a white black haired girl and that, before asking her name, Lola treated her nicely as she was opened to help her when Violetta asked it but, the moment she noticed cultural differences like her surname "Shevchenko" she immediately reacted violently as this conversation reflects on the new racist trend that haunted Britain since the beginning of Brexit, "xenophobia".

When recalling Paul Gilroy's words on this book "*There Ain't No Black In The Union Jack*"(1987) on race he said that this new contemporary notion of race was composed of various things and, in the book, although physically Violetta resembles Lola and both are being raised in the same town, it is the cultural and traditional differences of their origins that provoke Lola's rejectfulness towards Violetta because if Violetta had lied about her surname or denied her origins, Lola would have not probably questioned her as Lola's attitude demonstrates xenophobic tendencies because of her fear of the stranger which in this case, is Violetta.

3.3 Shevchenko's house

One of the most interesting chapters in *Summerwater* (2020), is the final chapter of the book titled "noise in his body" where we get to see through Jack's point of view what happened to Sevchenko's lodge.

In this chapter we see what is the "accidental" burning of the Svechenko's house, it is "accidental" because, Moss gives us several clues of who might have caused the fire as, when previously meeting Violetta, Lola reveals that

she likes lighters and that she found one on her mum's handbag (63), this added to the hatred she developed for Violetta and her family gives us a clue that she might have something to do with it as also, after the evacuation of the house, where Violetta goes missing, we get to see that Lola is present and she might have the lighter as in the book they describe "The other little girl, not Lola. Lola was still standing there, watching, her hand in her pocket, her smudged face and her hair pale in the firelight."(199). This might give us a clue that it was Lola who lit the fire inside the house.

The burning of the house of the Sevchenko's, not only is the book finale and a tragic event at the lodge but also portrays us the dangerous situation that immigrants face of in the UK as, since brexit started many Eastern European immigrants in the UK have faced numerous hostile and racist encounters because of the increase in hate against them as, in 2015 many UKIP members made certain declarations like:

"Nigel Farage, the former leader of UKIP, said he would prefer immigrants from India and Australia to East Europeans, even though he previously claimed his party would not want to discriminate against new arrivals by nationality."(Rzepnikowska 65)

This lack of respect and racist attitudes against eastern europeans has caused uncertainty, fear and many troubles to Eastern Europeans, specially to the Polish community (Rzepnikowska 67-72). We can see the aggression against Eastern Euopeans reflected on Summerwater (2020) as, to conclude, we can interpret that this fire is the aggressive destruction of the Eastern European community in the UK as, not only is their house burned, are mistreated and called different nationalities but also, they are the only family in Summerwater (2020) that do not get a chapter, being unable to show their perspectives or express themselves as we only see them as the "Bloody Bulgarians" (181) that live at the "(...) fucking Romanians place"(185).

4.Internal Racism (Scotland vs England)

As the book takes place in Scotland, most of the characters are Scottish except for one family. It is through them that, in Summerwater (2020) Moss is able to portray the tension between Scots and English residents.

The book of Summerwater (2020) is composed by several families who come from Scotland and live in cities like Glasgow or Edinburgh. One of the families that is enjoying their holidays on the lodge does not come from Scotland and, although they live in Edinburgh they come from England.

Although the English family tries to be nice and friendly to their neighbors they will face harsh comments from their fellow residents where they highlight their origins. In the chapter titled "*other silent swimmers*", we get to know more about this English family which is composed of 4 members being Claire, Jon, Izzie and Patrick.

There is one moment in the chapter where Claire comes out of the cabin while also Jon is outside playing with the kids and we hear this commentary "There's that other English family, they're saying, did I tell you now he's a teacher in Edinburgh? Aye, it's full of English these days, can't stand their own country any more." (116) It is clear that some of the residents do not like the presence of English citizens in Scotland. This comment contains two crucial aspects of the English-Scottish relationship dynamic as, in the first part, they allude to Jon as being "an English teacher in Edinburgh" which gives the impression that it is quite scandalous that there is an Englishman inside the Scottish educational system and, who is teaching Scottish people. It is also the last bit of the phrase that gives us one of the most important information and aspects of this dynamic as, in the comment, it is said "(...)can't stand their own country anymore" (116), this last bit of the phrase is the most interesting one because it creates a separation between Scotland and England as being two separate countries when, in reality, both belong to the UK.

There is another encounter where we face the same situation of England and Scotland being treated as two separate countries as, in the chapter titled "*once there stood* " where we get to meet the character of Becky, who is Alex's sister. In this chapter, she has an encounter with the English woman where she tries to be nice and polite and although Becky answers normally and politely she has the following thought "S'all right, Becky said, we're local ,see, used to it. Fuck off back to England,then, if you dont like it here, she didnt say."(147)

These two passages of the book reflect what we previously discussed when talking about Scotland as, although the UK is a country it is composed of different territories that are different from each other and, although they belong to the same nation, both England and Scotland share their differences. This resentment that Scottish people hold against the English has been reinforced since the two recent events that took place in Scotland being it the failed independence referendum in 2014 and Brexit as, Scotland was one of the principal “stay” region voter holders where more people hold a more European sentiment as we previously saw on chapter 2.2, when discussing internal racism.

We can appreciate the Scottish European identification in one of the book's passages titled “the audacity of small craft”. In this chapter, Alex, who is tired of being locked in the lodge decides to pick up his kayak and head to the river where he reflects on his life and future and, in one moment of his multiple reflections he says the following thing when talking about living outside Britain and moving to Australia, “They have farm jobs, don't they, for young travellers, for Europeans, and they'd stretch a point, wouldn't they, he is Scottish”(85). As we previously saw in chapter 2.2, Scottish European identity is talked about McEwen and Mitchell where they both talk about the Scottish vote to remain in the EU and also the sentiment of “my enemy's enemy” that Scotland decided to use, therefore becoming more closed with Europe. This issue is also explored by researcher Krishan Kumar in their text *“Negotiating English identity: Englishness, Britishness and the future of the United Kingdom”*(2010) where they argue about how the English people have always call themselves British and that the other territories like Wales and Scotland have prioritize their own identities rather than calling themselves British (475)

In this case, Alex not only says he is Scottish and European but he does not mention he is British, highlighting this aspect of Scottish identity of prioritizing the “Scottish” over the “British”. In conclusion, we can see how, although in short phrases and in a few moments of the book, how Moss does transport the national and identitarian conflict between Scotland and England, also

making an indirect reference to both Brexit results and the Scotland independence referendum of 2014.

In the next part of the paper we will talk about how Sarah Moss extrapolates his narrative universe of *Summerwater* (2020) to make reference to the modern British society where she talks about topics such as the decadence of the working class, racism or the post-Brexit society.

5. Isolation and Parody

5.1 Parody

One of the most interesting aspects of Sarah Moss' book is the aspect of Britain's parody. Sarah Moss sets us in an isolated landscape in the middle of the Scottish woods where several families from different backgrounds, social classes and countries will share a common space but, in reality, the representation of this common space and the different cabins represent a parody of modern Britain.

This parody of Britain starts with the protagonist of the book as, in *Summerwater* (2020) there is not an individual protagonist but rather a collective protagonist. Each chapter of the book is narrated through the perspective of a different character that is living a different situation as we might change from an old retired woman like Mary to a little girl from Glasgow like Lola. It is therefore that, we can argue that the book does not represent the story of an individual person but rather it is the story of a combined society of individuals who share a common language and some traditions.

Each one of the cabins represents a different social reality in which we get to see the representation that Moss constructs of the decadence of the working white English class.

The decadence of the white working class is represented through the frustration and uncertainty that the characters experience in the book. In Susan Condor and Steven Fenton's paper, "*Thinking across domains: Class, nation and racism in England and Britain*" (2012), we get an insight into Fenton's opinion on the downward class trajectory of the working class as he argues

"notes how working-class people experiencing a downward class trajectory tend to display a generalized sense of frustration and

resentment, which may be manifested in the form of anger about local or national decline and suspicion concerning immigration and multiculturalism”(389)

It is also worth mentioning that, apart from the resentment and frustration that these characters experience, we can also see that uncertainty and fear for the future is also a topic in the book.

This uncertainty might be influenced by Brexit as Daniel M. Knight argues in his paper “*Anxiety and Cosmopolitan futures*”(2017),“Brexit will be a permanent change but, with all the uncertainty, may never happen at all. The level of precariousness surrounding a deal that has permanent (or at least long-term) consequences” (239).

In one of the book chapters titled “*the audacity of small craft*”, we get to know that young Alex thinks about the future and what he wants to do with his life as he decides to leave the cabin to go with his kayak to the lake. In pages 87 and 88 of the book he starts to think about his situation saying that “He has been going to school for twelve years, three-quarters of his life (...)”(87), he then also starts to think what might be after that, reflecting on what things is he good at for him to study and then think about retirement and ends with the thought of what if, in the future there will be no planet (88).

These current thoughts added to his migration dreams of living in Australia that we get to see on page 84 shows us the frustration and anxiety of the British young working class as he is unable to see a future for himself.

Not only young characters in the book have these feelings but also the more mature one have it to as, in the chapter titled “*other silent swimmers*”, Claire also expresses a comment that also shares Alex’s frustrations for the future as she says “assuming no demented president has pressed his big red button and there is still air to breathe and water to drink, It was inexcusable, really to have children, the way things are, the way they’re going to be”(103).

The frustration shared by the cabin members, the racist attitude and blame on their problems to the noisy music of the Sevchenko family, the uncertainty, the racism and also the constant peaking and judging that goes on between the characters sets this book as a perfect representation and parody of Great

Britain as Moss combines different social topics to create this tiny representation of the UK.

5.2 Isolation

One of the things that we have learned from Brexit is that most of the reasons behind the “pro-Leaving vote” was an emotional rant on the topic of immigration that was aimed at the low working white classes who had felt left behind for many years (Goodwin 59-61). One of the main causes that Brexit has caused is that “Brexit has accelerated the polarization of values, outlooks, and priorities that increasingly divides university-educated cosmopolitans from poorly qualified nationalists.” (Goodwin 62)

It is this fragmentation between the cosmopolitan educated society that voted to remain in the EU and the working classes that have caused Britain to have become, not only a country that fails to create a sense of “Britishness” for Welsh and Scots who will rather maintain their own identities, but also a country that seems divided in terms of class and knowledge in which the youth wants to escape and the elders live miserably regretting to have brought up kids in this country.

It is through Sarah Moss’ literature that we are able to sense this aura of isolation that has been created around the UK as, not only is the UK, as, according to Carl and Denison “Britain is the least well-integrated EU member state: European, just not European enough”(Carl, Dennison 6) and it is this aura of insufficient integration in the European landscape that always made Britain as if it was never part of Europe.

This sense of aura has also been increased in the post-Brexit society as now the UK sees his cosmopolitanism at risk due to the new harsh immigration politics that have been created in the last few years as Britain now finds itself stuck between two paths that must be followed as

“Both of the main parties now have to wrestle with internal conflicts between Leavers and Remainers, between those who want to prioritize single-market access and those who want to prioritize stronger curbs on free movement and migration.”(Goodwin 62)

This two parties are reflected in *Summerwater* (2020) as, on the one hand we have characters who represent a more cosmopolitan and open minded youth

as, characters like Becky and Alex show a more internationally and open minded principles and ideas as, for example, Becky is the only character who tries to have a nice relationship with the Shevchenko family and, although she fails when she tries to talk in the local language of them, it is that effort that not only shows her open mindedness but also her tolerance and openness to learn new cultures.

On the other hand, there are characters who represent a more closed minded side of British society. Characters like Steve represent the working english class that has been fueled by conservative parties' discourse on immigration and that have a sense of rejection for people that, although they belong to the same ethnicity, they share different customs, language and traditions. Examples of Steve's attitude and, also his kids in chapters "*a woman sitting on the edge*" and "*a stone falling*", are a representation of this working class xenophobic individual whose main concern has become immigration.

It is in *Summerwater* (2020) that we can see how people judge between themselves as they look at themselves from their respective cabins who, in reality, serve as vessels to Moss in order to create her representation of Britain as each of them represent a different social class and reality that parodies Britain.

The social interactions between the characters and its social interactions between themselves mirror the post-Brexit society and they open up a space of negotiation that is able to also serve as a point of reflection for Britain's future. In her book Moss shows the "Underlying tensions between them have been exacerbated by the prominence of immigration in the referendum campaign, the democratic deficit in the EU, and the longer-term erosion of the welfare state."(Ashcroft,Bevir 1), this also adds the previous frustration, uncertainty and concerns about immigration who, have made Britain a country torn between cosmopolitanism and nationalism and who know sees itself farther from the EU as, Brexit terminated what was left of the European sentiment as "nearly two-thirds of Britons do not identify as European at all, compared to fewer than 40 percent of French and Italians, and fewer than 30 per cent of Spanish and Germans."(Carl,Dennison 1)

6. Conclusion

In this new post-Brexit era we have seen that Britain has been plagued with numerous social issues like its increase in racist violent encounters, frustration, uncertainty and also a noticeable division in the country's landscape.

It has been intriguing to find that the UK not only has become less open towards immigrants but also has seen violent encounters between themselves. In the novel we have seen how some characters like Becky that, although they do not say it out loud, they despise the English which, I find it is a matter of concern that rises more questions on what the future holds for the different territories that compose the United Kingdom as, how can both Scotland and England settle their differences when treating Brexit and their referendum? or, How can the sentiment of "Britishness" be translated to the Welsh, Northern Irish and Scottish citizens in order to create a more united and uniform country?

The lack of openness shown by some British characters in the novel make reference to real life situations as the Polish community has gone through hard times when co-existing with the rest of British society and it is true that since Brexit, we have seen how Britain has become less accessible even for EU members to access. It is this matter that also raises some questions about how Britain will deal with its multiculturalism and cosmopolitan nature? Will conservative politics prevail and prevent us, the migrants from ever trying to make a living in the UK?

Sarah Moss' *Summerwater* (2020) is not only an splendid piece of literature but is also a book that leaves you with many questions concerning various topics. The dark atmosphere and grayness of its Scottish landscape set the tone for what Britain has become, an isolated piece of land that has seen itself to become farther and farther away from European sentiment.

Its uniqueness and richness in characters allows the reader to identify with many of the different characters of the novel which in the end, represent us and you will always find something to identify with.

This book leaves you with many questions and concerns about how the world is going to treat Britain and how also Britain will treat itself.

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